

Coordinated Control of Multiple UAVs for Time-Critical Applications

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Abstract—The paper¹² proposes a solution to the problem of coordinated control of multiple unmanned air vehicles (UAVs) to ensure collision-free maneuvers under strict spatial and temporal constraints. The solution proposed relies on the decoupling of space and time in the problem formulation. First, a set of feasible trajectories are generated for all UAVs using a new direct method of optimal control that takes into account rules for collision avoidance. A by-product of this step yields for each vehicle a spatial path to be followed, together with a desired nominal speed profile along that path. Each vehicle is then asked to execute a pure path following maneuver in three-dimensional space by resorting to a novel 3-D algorithm that enforces temporal constraints aimed at coordinating the fleet of vehicles. Simulations illustrate the potential of the methodology developed.

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1. Introduction

This paper addresses the problem of coordinated control of multiple unmanned air vehicles (UAVs) under tight spatial and temporal constraints. This topic of research is motivated by the need to develop strategies for coordinated ground target suppression and sequential autolandings for multiple UAVs. Both mission scenarios require a group of UAVs to

execute time-critical maneuvers in close proximity of each other. For the case of ground target suppression, a formation of UAVs must break up and execute a coordinated maneuver to arrive at a predefined position over the target at a given time. Similarly, for the case of sequential autolandings, a formation must also break up and arrive at the assigned glideslope point separated by pre-specified safe-guarding time intervals. A key requirement underlying these missions is that all maneuvers be collision-free.

In recent years, there has been widespread interest in the problem of coordinated motion control of fleets of autonomous vehicles. Applications include aircraft and spacecraft formation flying [1]-[4], coordinated control of land robots [5]-[6], and control of multiple surface and underwater vehicles [7]-[10]. The work reported in the literature addresses a large class of topics that include, among others, leader/follower formation flying, control of the center of mass and radius of dispersion of swarms of vehicles, and uniform coverage of an area by a group of surveying robots. There are, however, applications with UAVs that do not fit the scenarios commonly described in the literature. Namely, the missions described in the present work that include spatial as well as temporal requirements.

To deal with the new scenarios, a methodology for coordinated control of UAVs is proposed that unfolds in two basic steps. First, a set of feasible trajectories are generated for all UAVs using a direct method of optimal control that takes explicitly into account the boundary initial and final conditions, the simplified UAV dynamics, and safety rules for collision avoidance. This is done by resorting to an extension of the work reported in [11] to multiple UAVs. A by-product of this step yields - for each vehicle - a spatial path to be followed, together with a desired nominal speed profile along that path. The second step consists of making each vehicle execute a path following maneuver along its assigned path, while enforcing temporal constraints aimed at coordinating the fleet of vehicles. This is achieved by using a new nonlinear path

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² IEEEAC paper #1036, Version 3, Updated Oct., 24 2005.

following algorithm in three-dimensional space that generalizes the one introduced in [5] for wheeled robots and by manipulating the speed of progression along the path about the nominal assigned speed. Clearly, the methodology proposed relies on the decoupling of space and time in the problem formulation. The rationale for this procedure stems from the fact that path following controllers are easier to design than trajectory tracking controllers and, when properly designed, yield smooth approaching maneuvers to the spatial curves that must be tracked. At the same time, this strategy will naturally generate the control activity that is required to capture the nominal paths generated during the path planning phase, even if due to unforeseen disturbances the vehicle deviates too much from it.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the methodology adopted for near-optimal real-time UAV trajectory generation. Section 3 offers a solution to the problem of path following in 3D. Finally, Section 4 includes the results of simulations with the nonlinear dynamic models of a small fleet of UAVs.

2. Near-Optimal Real-Time Trajectories Generation

This section discusses the algorithm used for real-time trajectory generation for multiple UAVs. First, the case of a single UAV is addressed as in [11]. These results are then generalized to the case of multiple UAVs.

UAV Model

Let $\{I\}$ denote a local level coordinate system with x -axis pointing East, y – North, and z – Up. Then the set of point-mass equations for the UAV's coordinates (x, y, z) , speed v , flight path angle γ , heading ψ , and mass m , assuming flat Earth, and small side-slip angle has the following well known form [11]-[12]:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= v \cos \gamma \cos \psi, & \dot{v} &= g(n_x - \sin \gamma), \\ \dot{y} &= -v \cos \gamma \sin \psi, & \dot{\gamma} &= \frac{g}{v}(n_z \cos \phi - \cos \gamma), \\ \dot{z} &= v \sin \gamma, & \dot{\psi} &= -\frac{g}{v \cos \gamma} n_z \sin \phi, \\ & & \dot{m} &= -C_s, \\ \dot{\bar{n}} &= \frac{k_T \delta_T - \bar{n}}{t_s}, n_x = \frac{T(\delta_T, \bar{n}) - D}{mg}, n_z = \frac{L}{mg}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In (1) n_x and n_z denote longitudinal and normal components of the load factor, that depend on the current thrust T , drag D , and lift L , g is the acceleration due to gravity). In turn, thrust T depends on relative thrust (throttle setting) δ_T and engine's revolutions per second \bar{n} . The dynamics for \bar{n} are modeled by a first order differential equation. The

remaining two include the bank angle ϕ and the fuel consumption C_s . Thus, $\xi = \{x, y, z, v, \gamma, \psi, m\}^T$ is the state vector for a UAV and $\mathbf{u} = \{\delta_T, n_z, \phi\}^T$ is the vector of control inputs. The restrictions on control inputs are of the form $\delta_T \in [\delta_{T \min}; \delta_{T \max}]$, $n_z \in [n_{z \min}; n_{z \max}]$, $|\phi| \leq \phi_{\max}$. The restrictions on their derivatives take into account engine build-up and thrust-decay times as well as the characteristics of UAV's control system.

Reference Functions for Local Level Coordinates

We assume that the position states x , y and z can be represented by algebraic polynomials of degree n with the independent parameter $s \in [0; s_f]$, where s_f is the virtual path length considered to be the first optimization parameter. This makes it possible to define UAV's position states as follows:

$$x_i(s) = \sum_{k=0}^n a_{ik} \frac{(\max(1, k-2))! s^k}{k!}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (2)$$

(where for notational convenience we set $x_1=x$, $x_2=y$ and $x_3=z$).

The degree n of the polynomial $x_i(s)$, is determined by whether boundary conditions to be satisfied include constraints on position; position and velocity; position, velocity and acceleration. The coefficients of the polynomials in (2) are determined by satisfying the boundary conditions. We denote the number of initial condition constraints by d_0 and final condition constraints by d_f . Then the minimal degree of each polynomial in (2) is $n^* = d_0 + d_f + 1$. It is important to point out that the parameterization (2) completely determines the spatial profile of the UAV. The trajectory that can be followed with a variety of speed profiles, since we have separated trajectory and speed (and haven't touched the latter yet).

Now, varying the length of the virtual path s_f changes the look of the trajectory, therefore providing the flexibility for deconfliction in case of multiple UAVs. Furthermore, using $n > n^*$ allows for more variable parameters and therefore for more flexible trajectories (increasing however the required CPU time for optimization). A complete discussion of this subject can be found in [11] and [13].

Determination of the Velocity Profile

The UAV velocity along the path defined in (2) $v(s)$ may be determined in two ways. The first approach is to integrate the corresponding equations of motion using given thrust vs. time profile to yield

$$v'(s) = g(n_x - \sin \gamma) \frac{dt}{ds} = \frac{g(n_x - \sin \gamma)}{\lambda(s)}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\lambda(s) = \frac{ds}{dt} \quad (4)$$

represents velocity along the virtual path s . For instance, consider the on/off throttle control for landing approach (nominal power at the beginning and idle at the end). If we set a single throttle switching point from $\delta_{T_{\max}}$ to $\delta_{T_{\min}}$ to occur at the moment t_r^* (s_r^*), then the search for the near-optimal control will be made over admissible path length $0 \leq s_r^* \leq s_f$ (relative thrust \bar{T} then can be calculated with regard to the thrust build-up time and thrust-decay time). The second approach is to predefine a separate reference polynomial function for $v(s)$.

Solution of the Inverse Dynamics Problem

The trajectory parameters are determined numerically at N points equally spaced over the virtual path with increments

$$\Delta s = s_f (N-1)^{-1}.$$

This corresponds to the time intervals

$$\Delta t_j = v^{-1} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^3 (x_{i,j+1} - x_{i,j})^2}, \quad (j = \overline{1, N-1}).$$

Using Δs and Δt_j , the parameter λ (4) is calculated at each step. Explicit expressions for UAV position (2), with the velocity (3) calculated at the corresponding time instants, uniquely determine all the motion parameters: $\gamma(t)$, $\psi(t)$, $\phi(t)$ and $n_z(t)$, [11], [13].

It should be emphasized here that for cooperative control applications, optimization of the trajectories itself, say from the standpoint of minimum time or minimum fuel, is not the major goal. Deconfliction and feasibility of the trajectories for the flock of UAVs, - that's where the main accent shifts and that's where the power of the suggested direct method is.

Trajectory Optimization Algorithm

Summarizing aforementioned steps, the trajectory generation algorithm includes the following steps.

1. Using an arbitrary value of the virtual path length s_f and a set of free polynomial coefficients \mathfrak{K} (when $n > n^*$), compute the reference polynomial (2).

2. Using arbitrary initial guess of the throttle switching parameter s_r^* , integrate equation (3) over the interval $s \in [0; s_f]$ with the integration step Δs .

3. Using inverse dynamics and expressions (2) and (3) obtain the values for UAV states and controls [11], [13]-[14]. At the end of the trajectory, compute the functional J and the penalty function G expressed as a weighted difference of the final velocity errors and constraint violations.

4. Iterate over steps 1-3 to solve a minimization problem of the following form

$$\Xi_{opt} = \arg \min_{G(\Xi) < \varepsilon} J(\Xi),$$

where the parameter space $\Xi = \{s_f; \mathfrak{K}, s_r^*\} \in R^3$, and ε is the predefined tolerance.

This problem can be effectively solved with the help of any zero-order method, e.g. the Nelder-Mead downhill simplex algorithm or the Hooke-Jeeves pattern direct search algorithm. Of course, both algorithms should be modified in order to search the functional extremum only when penalty function is less than specified value (correspondent scripts were written in MATLAB). The weights of the penalty function G are chosen heuristically to ensure the specified accuracy when matching the terminal value of the UAV's velocity and all the restrictions.

Setting the cost functional $J = s_f$ corresponds to the time-optimal control problem. However, any other parameter, different from the time t_f , or even a combination of several parameters can be used to define J . This is one of the main advantages of the direct method. Two other advantages include: *i*) intuitively understandable analytic presentation of near-optimal solution, and *ii*) convergence robustness.

Extension to Multiple UAVs

For the case of multiple UAVs, say M UAVs, the dimension of the problem increases to $3M$. To guarantee collision avoidance two sets of constraints are added (corresponding errors are added to the penalty function G). The first one introduces a scheduled (with interval Δ) arrival at the top of the glide slope:

$$t_f^1 - t_f^2 = t_f^2 - t_f^3 = \dots = t_f^{M-1} - t_f^M = \Delta.$$

The second one takes care of the collision avoidance (assuming minimal separation of E):

$$\min_{\substack{j,k=1,\dots,M \\ j \neq k}} \sum_{i=1}^3 (x_i^j - x_i^k)^2 \geq E^2.$$

Numerical Examples

As an example, Fig.1 illustrates flexibility of the reference polynomials to compute a coordinated sequential (time-optimum for each UAV and collision free) target suppression mission by three UAVs. Fig.2 shows that this approach can be easily extended to compute an entire landing approach trajectory (this trajectory does not require glideslope tracking). Finally, Fig.3 shows an example of trajectory generation for a scheduled arrival at the top of the glideslope for a cluster of three UAVs initially flying in compact formation.

Figure 1 - Coordinated attack trajectories

Figure 2 - Example of landing approach trajectory

Figure 3 - Scheduled cooperative glideslope capture

3. Path Following of Polynomial Trajectories

The algorithm for trajectory generation introduced in Section 2 yields - for each vehicle - a spatial path to be followed, together with the corresponding nominal speed profile. To follow the paths computed, this section describes a path following algorithm that extends that in [5] to a 3-D setting and introduces a further modification aimed at meeting time-critical inter-vehicle constraints. At this level, only the simplified kinematic equations of the vehicle will

be addressed by taking pitch rate and yaw rate as virtual outer-loop control inputs. The dynamics will be dealt with at a later stage by introducing an inner-loop control law.

The notation required is introduced next (Fig.4). The frame $\{I\}$ introduced in the previous section denotes a local level coordinate system with x -axis pointing East, y - North, and z - Up. We let $\{F\}$ be a Serret-Frenet frame attached to the path, and $\{W\}$ the wind frame attached to the UAV. We denote by ${}^F\omega_{FI}$ the angular velocity of $\{F\}$ with respect to $\{I\}$ resolved in $\{F\}$. Let $\mathbf{p}_c(s)$, where s denotes the virtual arc length introduced in previous section, be the path to be followed and let Q denote the center of mass of the aircraft.

Further let P be an arbitrary point on the path that plays the role of a "virtual" aircraft to be followed. This is in contrast with the set-up for path following originally proposed in [16] where P was simply defined as the point on the path that is closest to the vehicle. Since this point may not be uniquely defined, the strategy in [16] led to very conservative estimates for the region of attraction about the path to be followed. Endowing P with an extra degree of freedom (that will be exploited later) is the key to the algorithm presented in [5] that is extended in this paper to the 3-D case. Point Q can be resolved in $\{I\}$ as $\mathbf{q}_I = [x, y, z]^T$ or in $\{F\}$ as $\mathbf{q}_F = [s_1, y_1, z_1]^T$, so that $\mathbf{q}_I = \mathbf{p}_c + \mathbf{q}_F$. From the previous section, the simplified UAV kinematic equations can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = v \cos \gamma \cos \psi \\ \dot{y} = -v \cos \gamma \sin \psi \\ \dot{z} = v \sin \gamma \\ \dot{\gamma} = u_1 \\ \dot{\psi} = u_2, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where u_1 and u_2 denote the virtual control inputs pitch rate and yaw rate, respectively. Following standard nomenclature [17]-[18]

$$\mathbf{T}(s) := \left\| \frac{d\mathbf{p}(s)}{ds} \right\|^{-1} \frac{d\mathbf{p}(s)}{ds}, \quad \mathbf{N}(s) := \left\| \frac{d\mathbf{T}(s)}{ds} \right\|^{-1} \frac{d\mathbf{T}(s)}{ds}$$

and

$$\mathbf{B}(s) = \mathbf{T}(s) \times \mathbf{N}(s)$$

denote the tangent, normal, and binormal, respectively to the path. The vectors \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{N} , \mathbf{B} are orthonormal and define the basis vectors of $\{F\}$ as well as the rotation matrix ${}^I\mathbf{R} = [\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{B}]$ from $\{F\}$ to $\{I\}$. It is well known that

$${}^F\omega_{FI} = [\zeta \dot{s}, 0, \kappa \dot{s}]^T, \quad \text{where } \kappa(s) := \left\| \frac{d\mathbf{T}(s)}{ds} \right\|$$

is the curvature of $P_c(s)$ and $\zeta(s) := \pm \left\| \frac{d\mathbf{B}(s)}{ds} \right\|$ is its torsion.

Figure 4 - Problem geometry

Now, from the one hand, using the notation above (see Fig.4) we may state that

$$\mathbf{q}_I = \mathbf{p}_c(s) + {}^I\mathbf{R}\mathbf{q}_F,$$

so that the full derivative of this expression becomes

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_I = {}^I\mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{z} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + {}^I\mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{s}_1 \\ \dot{y}_1 \\ \dot{z}_1 \end{bmatrix} + {}^I\mathbf{R} \left({}^F\boldsymbol{\omega}_{FI} \times \begin{bmatrix} \dot{s}_1 \\ \dot{y}_1 \\ \dot{z}_1 \end{bmatrix} \right).$$

From the other hand the derivative $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_I$ can be expressed

directly in $\{F\}$ as $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_I = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix}$. Equating two expressions for

$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_I$ we get

$${}^F\mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{s}(1 - \kappa y_1) + \dot{s}_1 \\ \dot{y}_1 + \dot{s}(\kappa s_1 - \zeta z_1) \\ \dot{z}_1 + \zeta \dot{s} y_1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Additionally noting that

$${}^F\mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} = {}^F\mathbf{R} {}^W\mathbf{R} {}^I\mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} = {}^F\mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

we finally obtain

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{s}_1 \\ \dot{y}_1 \\ \dot{z}_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\dot{s}(1 - \kappa y_1) \\ -\dot{s}(\kappa s_1 - \zeta z_1) \\ -\zeta \dot{s} y_1 \end{bmatrix} + {}^F\mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Let $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_e = [\phi_e, \theta_e, \psi_e]^T$ denote the vector of Euler angles that parameterize locally the rotation matrix from $\{F\}$ to $\{W\}$. Then,

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_e = \mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_e) {}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{WF},$$

where

$$\mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_e) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sin \phi_e \tan \theta_e & \cos \phi_e \tan \theta_e \\ 0 & \cos \phi_e & -\sin \phi_e \\ 0 & \frac{\sin \phi_e}{\cos \theta_e} & \frac{\cos \phi_e}{\cos \theta_e} \end{bmatrix}$$

is nonsingular for $\theta_e \neq \pm \frac{\pi}{2}$ and ${}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{WF}$ denotes the angular velocity of $\{W\}$ with respect to $\{F\}$ resolved in $\{W\}$.

We may further express ${}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{WF}$ as

$${}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{WF} = {}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{WI} - {}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{FI}.$$

Next, since

$${}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{WI} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \dot{\gamma} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \cos \gamma & 0 & -\sin \gamma \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \gamma & 0 & \cos \gamma \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\dot{\psi} \sin \gamma \\ \dot{\gamma} \\ \dot{\psi} \cos \gamma \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$${}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{FI} = {}^W\mathbf{R} {}^F\boldsymbol{\omega}_{FI} = {}^W\mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} \zeta \dot{s} \\ 0 \\ \kappa \dot{s} \end{bmatrix} \quad [18],$$

we obtain that

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_e = \mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_e) ({}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{WI} - {}^W\boldsymbol{\omega}_{FI}) = \begin{bmatrix} -\dot{\psi} \sin \gamma + \dot{\gamma} \sin \phi_e \tan \theta_e + \dot{\psi} \cos \gamma \cos \phi_e \tan \theta_e \\ \dot{\gamma} \cos \phi_e - \dot{\psi} \sin \phi_e \cos \gamma + \sin \psi_e \zeta \dot{s} \\ \dot{\gamma} \frac{\sin \phi_e}{\cos \theta_e} + \dot{\psi} \cos \gamma \frac{\cos \phi_e}{\cos \theta_e} - \dot{s} (s \tan \theta_e \cos \psi_e + \kappa) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

Note that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\theta}_e \\ \dot{\psi}_e \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \psi_e \zeta \dot{s} \\ -\dot{s} (\zeta \tan \theta_e \cos \psi_e + \kappa) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi_e & -\sin \phi_e \cos \gamma \\ \frac{\sin \phi_e}{\cos \theta_e} & \cos \gamma \frac{\cos \phi_e}{\cos \theta_e} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\gamma} \\ \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix} =: \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{G} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\gamma} \\ \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{G} is nonsingular for all $\gamma \neq \pm \frac{\pi}{2}$.

Let

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\gamma} \\ \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{G}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} u_\theta \\ u_\psi \end{bmatrix} - \mathbf{D} \right\}, \quad (8)$$

where $\begin{bmatrix} u_\theta \\ u_\psi \end{bmatrix}$ is an auxiliary vector to be determined later.

Then, by combining equations (5) and (4) we obtain the equations for the (path following) error dynamics:

$$G_e = \begin{cases} \dot{s}_1 = -\dot{s}(1 - \kappa y_1) + v \cos \theta_e \cos \psi_e \\ \dot{y}_1 = -\dot{s}(\kappa s_1 - \zeta z_1) + v \cos \theta_e \sin \psi_e \\ \dot{z}_1 = -\zeta \dot{s} y_1 - v \sin \theta_e \\ \dot{\theta}_e = u_\theta \\ \dot{\psi}_e = u_\psi \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Notice how the rate of progression ds/dt of point P along the path becomes an extra variable that can be manipulated at will. A globally asymptotically stable (GAS) control law is

now derived for G_e to drive all error variables to 0 using u_θ and u_ψ as control inputs. To this effect, consider the candidate Lyapunov function

$$V = \frac{1}{2}(s_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2) + \frac{1}{2c_1}(\theta_e - \delta_\theta)^2 + \frac{1}{2c_2}(\psi_e - \delta_\psi)^2, \quad (10)$$

where

$$\delta_\theta = \sin^{-1} \left(\text{sign}(v) \theta_1 \frac{z_1}{|z_1| + \varepsilon} \right)$$

and

$$\delta_\psi = \sin^{-1} \left(\text{sign}(v \cos \theta_e) \theta_2 \frac{-y_1}{|y_1| + \varepsilon} \right) \quad (11)$$

for some $\theta_1 > 0$, $\theta_2 > 0$ and $\varepsilon > 0$. Inspired by the work of Samson, the above equations capture “desired” approach angles to the path. Computing the time-derivative of V yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} &= s_1 \dot{s}_1 + y_1 \dot{y}_1 + z_1 \dot{z}_1 + \frac{\theta_e - \delta_\theta}{c_1} (\dot{\theta}_e - \dot{\delta}_\theta) + \frac{\psi_e - \delta_\psi}{c_2} (\dot{\psi}_e - \dot{\delta}_\psi) = \\ &= s_1 (-\dot{s}(1 - \kappa y_1) + v \cos \theta_e \cos \psi_e) + y_1 (-\dot{s}(\kappa s_1 - \zeta z_1) + v \cos \theta_e \sin \psi_e) + z_1 (-\zeta \dot{s} y_1 - v \sin \theta_e) + \\ &+ \frac{\theta_e - \delta_\theta}{c_1} (u_\theta - \dot{\delta}_\theta) + \frac{\psi_e - \delta_\psi}{c_2} (u_\psi - \dot{\delta}_\psi) = s_1 (-\dot{s} + v \cos \theta_e \cos \psi_e) + y_1 v \cos \theta_e \sin \psi_e - z_1 v \sin \theta_e + \\ &+ \frac{\theta_e - \delta_\theta}{c_1} (u_\theta - \dot{\delta}_\theta) + \frac{\psi_e - \delta_\psi}{c_2} (u_\psi - \dot{\delta}_\psi) + y_1 v \cos \theta_e \sin \delta_\psi - y_1 v \cos \theta_e \sin \delta_\psi - z_1 v \sin \delta_\theta + z_1 v \sin \delta_\theta. \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{s} &= K_1 s_1 + v \cos \theta_e \cos \psi_e \\ u_\theta &= -K_2 (\theta_e - \delta_\theta) + c_1 z_1 v \frac{\sin \theta_e - \sin \delta_\theta}{\theta_e - \delta_\theta} + \dot{\delta}_\theta \\ u_\psi &= -K_3 (\psi_e - \delta_\psi) - c_2 y_1 v \cos \theta_e \frac{\sin \psi_e - \sin \delta_\psi}{\psi_e - \delta_\psi} + \dot{\delta}_\psi \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $K_1 > 0$, $K_2 > 0$, $K_3 > 0$ (the latter two expressions can be used in (8)). Then

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} &= -K_1 s_1^2 - K_2 \frac{(\theta_e - \delta_\theta)^2}{c_1} - K_3 \frac{(\psi_e - \delta_\psi)^2}{c_2} - \\ &+ K_4 v_e^2 + y_1 v \cos \theta_e \sin \delta_\psi - z_1 v \sin \delta_\theta = \\ &= -K_1 s_1^2 - K_2 \frac{(\theta_e - \delta_\theta)^2}{c_1} - K_3 \frac{(\psi_e - \delta_\psi)^2}{c_2} - \\ &+ \theta_1 \frac{y_1^2}{|y_1| + \varepsilon} |v \cos \theta_e| - \theta_2 \frac{z_1^2}{|z_1| + \varepsilon} |v| < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

thus proving global attractivity to the path as long as $v(t)$ does not tend to 0 as t grows unbounded. The control law given by (8) and (12) guarantees “time-independent” tracking of a single trajectory because it is assumed that a desired speed profile for $v(t)$ is set in advance. We now extend this circle of ideas to deal with the case of time critical missions for multiple UAVs. In particular, we are interested in having each UAV reach the end of its trajectory at a pre-specified time of arrival. To account for time-of-arrival error we introduce new variables: $s_{f,i}$ - desired arc length of the trajectory of the i^{th} UAV, $t_{oa,i}$ - desired time of arrival of the i^{th} UAV, and $v_{d,i}$ - desired velocity profile along i^{th} trajectory obtained using direct methods. Clearly,

$$s_{f,i} = s_f(t_1) + \int_{t_1}^{t_{oa}} v_d dt,$$

where t_1 represents current time. Notice also that the actual path length $s_{a,i}$ is given by

$$s_{a,i} = s(t_1) + \int_{t_1}^{t_{oa}} v dt.$$

As a consequence, the total path error becomes $\Delta s_i = s_{f,i} - s_{a,i}$ and its derivative is $\Delta \dot{s}_i = v_{d,i} - v_i$. After enlarging the error variables to include Δs_i , the complete generalized error dynamics for the i^{th} vehicle can be written as

$$G_{e,i} = \begin{cases} \dot{s}_{1,i} = -\dot{s}_i(1 - \kappa_i y_{1,i}) + v_i \cos \theta_{e,i} \cos \psi_{e,i} \\ \dot{y}_{1,i} = -\dot{s}_i(\kappa_i s_{1,i} - \zeta_i z_{1,i}) + v_i \cos \theta_{e,i} \sin \psi_{e,i} \\ \dot{z}_{1,i} = -\zeta_i \dot{s}_i y_{1,i} - v_i \sin \theta_{e,i} \\ \dot{\theta}_{e,i} = u_{\theta,i} \\ \dot{\psi}_{e,i} = u_{\psi,i} \\ \Delta \dot{s}_i = v_{d,i} - v_i \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Let

$$V_i = \frac{1}{2}(s_{1,i}^2 + y_{1,i}^2 + z_{1,i}^2) + \frac{1}{2c_1}(\theta_{e,i} - \delta_{\theta,i})^2 + \frac{1}{2c_2}(\psi_{e,i} - \delta_{\psi,i})^2 + \frac{1}{2}\Delta s_i^2 \quad (15)$$

Then the control law

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{s}_i &= K_{1,i} s_{1,i} + v_i \cos \theta_{e,i} \cos \psi_{e,i} \\ u_{\theta,i} &= -K_{2,i}(\theta_{e,i} - \delta_{\theta,i}) + c_{1,i} z_{1,i} v_i \frac{\sin \theta_{e,i} - \sin \delta_{\theta,i}}{\theta_{e,i} - \delta_{\theta,i}} + \dot{\delta}_{\theta,i} \\ u_{\psi,i} &= -K_{3,i}(\psi_{e,i} - \delta_{\psi,i}) \\ &\quad - c_{2,i} y_{1,i} v_i \cos \theta_{e,i} \frac{\sin \psi_{e,i} - \sin \delta_{\psi,i}}{\psi_{e,i} - \delta_{\psi,i}} + \dot{\delta}_{\psi,i} \\ v_i &= K_{4,i} \Delta \tau_i + v_{d,i} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

stabilizes the origin of system $G_{e,i}$. This can be easily shown by direct substitution of (15) into the expression for \dot{V}_i . Expression (8) can be used to compute the corresponding yaw rate and pitch rate commands for each UAV.

4. Simulations

The nonlinear path following algorithm derived in Section 2 relied on a kinematic model of the vehicle under consideration. The final control law manipulates directly pitch and yaw rate, which should be viewed as virtual control inputs in the outer loop of inner-outer control architecture. An inner loop must be designed at a later stage

to actually generate the required pitch and yaw rate commands. This problem will not be addressed here. Instead, we assume that an inner loop autopilot is available that yields adequate performance. The control law (16) was implemented on the nonlinear 6DOF model of a Telemaster UAV used at NPS (see Fig.5).

Figure 5 – Modified Telemaster UAV (wing span 2.5m, take-off weight 8kg)

Control commands generated by (8) and (16) were used to drive the inner loop autopilot currently implemented on the Piccolo autopilot onboard Telemaster as shown in Fig.6.

Figure 6 - Inner/outer control structure

Figure 7 includes the results of a nonlinear simulation of a sequential autoland by three Telemasters. Each UAV is required to arrive at the top of glideslope 60 sec apart with the leader arriving 280 sec from the autoland initiation. Table 1 contains time of arrival results for each UAV.

Table 1. Times of arrival at the top of glideslope

UAV 1	UAV 2	UAV 3
278.1s	338.0s	400.8s

Figure 8 shows the path following errors exhibited by each UAV during the maneuver. Clearly, errors in y and z channels are very small illustrating good tracking performance. Notice that values for s_1 vary significantly – however - by design this has no impact on performance.

Figures 9 includes the pitch and roll response by each UAV and shows that the polynomial trajectories being tracked required feasible roll and pitch angles.

Figure 7 -- The 3D view (a) and top view (b) of the sequential autoland simulation

Figure 8 - Path following errors arisen during the sequential autoland simulation

Figure 9 - Pitch and roll angles time histories

5. Summary

The paper presents the theory and practical implementation of on-line generation of near-optimal collision-free trajectories for UAV formation and their following automatic tracking. The results of simulations and preliminary flight tests demonstrate a great potential of the developed algorithms.

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